

Kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of thiosemicarbazide by substituted-*N*-chlorobenzamides in aqueous methanol medium

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The kinetics of oxidation of thiosemicarbazide by *N*-chlorobenzamide, *N*-chloro-*p*-methyl-, *N*-chloro-*p*-chloro- and *N*-chloro-*p*-nitrobenzamides have been studied in aqueous methanol in the presence of perchloric acid. The reactions show first order kinetics in [oxidant], fractional order in [TSC] and inverse first order in [H⁺]. The rates slightly decrease with increase in ionic strength of the medium (0.05–0.50 mol dm⁻³), but increase with decrease in dielectric constant of the medium, effected by increasing the methanol composition of the solvent. Addition of the reduced product of the oxidant, benzamide has no significant effect on the rate. The observed results have been explained by a two-pathway mechanism and the related rate law deduced. Activation parameters for both the pathways have been evaluated by computing the rate coefficients for both the pathways at different temperatures. The activation parameters have also been optimised corresponding to the parent oxidant. The constancy of the free energies of activation may signal the operation of similar mechanism. Validity of Hammett equation and isokinetic relationship has also been tested.

N-Chlorobenzamide has been employed both as oxidant and chlorinating agent for studying a number of reactions¹. The oxidative strength of the *N*-chlorobenzamide depends on the ease with which Cl⁺ is released from the reagent, as Cl⁺ is the effective oxidising species in the reactions of *N*-chloroamides. The ease with which Cl⁺ is released from the *N*-chloroamide depends on the quantum of electron density on the nitrogen atom of the amide group. This in turn depends on the nature of the substituent in the benzene ring as electron donating groups increase the electron density on the nitrogen atom, while the electron withdrawing groups lower it. As a result, with electron-withdrawing groups in the benzene ring, Cl⁺ is released much more easily than with the electron-donating groups in the benzene ring of

substituted *N*-chlorobenzamides. Thus it is possible to produce an oxidant of desired strength by introducing an appropriate group in the benzene ring of the *N*-chloroarylamide. As a part of our efforts in the direction of introducing oxidants or reagents of varying strength, we have prepared several substituted *N*-chlorobenzamides (SNCB) and employed them for studying the kinetics of oxidation of thiosemicarbazide (TSC) in aqueous methanol medium. We report herein the kinetics of oxidation of thiosemicarbazide by *N*-chlorobenzamide (NCB) and SNCB : *N*-chloro-*p*-methylbenzamide (NCMB), *N*-chloro-*p*-chlorobenzamide (NCCB) and *N*-chloro-*p*-nitrobenzamide (NCNB) and correlate the results.

Table 1. Pseudo-first order rate constants (k_{obs}) for the oxidation of TSC by substituted *N*-chlorobenzamides (SNCB) in aqueous methanol (1 : 1, v/v) in the presence of perchloric acid

$I = 0.3 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, Temp. = 303 K			$10^4 k_{\text{obs}} (\text{s}^{-1})$ for $p\text{-X-C}_6\text{H}_4\text{CONHCl}$, where X =			
$10^3 [\text{SNCB}]_0$ mol dm ⁻³	$10^2 [\text{TSC}]_0$ mol dm ⁻³	$10^2 [\text{HClO}_4]$ mol dm ⁻³	H	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	<i>p</i> -Cl	<i>p</i> -NO ₂
Effect of varying [oxidant] ₀ :						
0.2	1.0	10.0	4.4	3.9	5.2	5.6
0.5	1.0	10.0	4.5	4.0	5.2	5.4
1.0	1.0	10.0	4.6	3.9	5.3	5.2
2.0	1.0	10.0	4.5	3.9	5.6	5.2
Effect of varying [HClO ₄] ₀ :						
1.0	1.0	1.0	44.0	38.4	57.2	54.6
1.0	1.0	2.0	23.0	18.5	24.8	31.9
1.0	1.0	3.0	12.5	11.0	14.4	16.6
1.0	1.0	5.0	7.8	7.5	9.1	10.0
1.0	1.0	10.0	4.5	3.9	5.3	5.2
1.0	1.0	20.0	2.1	2.0	2.6	2.9

Table 2. Pseudo-first order rate constants (k_{obs}) for the oxidation of TSC by substituted *N*-chlorobenzamides (SNCB) in aqueous methanol (1 : 1, v/v) in the presence of perchloric acid as [TSC] is varied at different temperatures

$10^3 [\text{SNCB}] = 10 [\text{HClO}_4] = 3.33, I = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$
 $10^2 [\text{TSC}]_0$
 mol dm^{-3}

$10^5 k_{\text{obs}} (\text{s}^{-1})$ at different T (K) for $p\text{-X-C}_6\text{H}_4\text{CONHCl}$, where $X =$

	H				<i>p</i> -CH ₃				<i>p</i> -Cl				<i>p</i> -NO ₂			
	293	298	303	308	293	298	303	308	293	298	303	308	293	298	303	308
0.5	11.0	31.0	42.0	71.0	15.4	28.5	40.5	119	16.5	30.7	52.3	96.6	13.6	30.7	50.6	104
1.0	14.0	33.0	46.0	78.0	17.1	30.2	42.0	127	17.4	32.9	53.2	101	16.5	32.6	52.3	111
2.0	18.0	37.0	64.0	90.0	19.0	35.9	52.3	131	18.7	37.9	62.5	108	19.2	38.4	58.0	115
3.0	20.0	51.0	76.0	118	24.5	42.0	69.0	149	23.6	47.8	80.8	148	23.0	43.5	67.7	128
5.0	–	75.0	119	134	44.3	56.4	95.0	174	35.1	58.3	99.7	209	39.4	72.0	99.4	174

There are very few reports on the mechanistic aspects of thiosemicarbazide oxidation². Kinetics of oxidation of thiosemicarbazide by *N*-halo, *N*-metallo and *N,N*-dihalo aromatic sulfonamides and other oxidants have been reported.

Results and Discussion

The kinetic data on the oxidation of thiosemicarbazide by *N*-chlorobenzamide, *N*-chloro-*p*-methylbenzamide, *N*-chloro-*p*-chlorobenzamide and *N*-chloro-*p*-nitrobenzamide under varying [SNCB], [TSC], [HClO₄], solution composition and temperature in aqueous methanol medium are shown in Tables 1 and 2.

Effect of varying [NCSB]₀ : At constant [TSC]₀ (5–50 fold excess over [SNCB]₀) and [H⁺], first order plots of log [SNCB] versus time were linear up to at least 75% completion of the reaction. The pseudo-first order rate constants (k_{obs}) computed from the plots remained unaffected by the changes in [SNCB] (Table 1), establishing first order dependence of the rate on [SNCB] in all the cases.

Effect of varying [TSC]₀ : At constant [SNCB]₀ and [HClO₄] under substrate excess conditions (5–50 fold excess over [SNCB]), the rates increased with increase in [TSC] with fractional order dependences in all the cases (Table 2). The rates of the reactions with the variation of [TSC] were measured at different temperatures (Table 2). The direct plots of k_{obs} versus [substrate] gave better correlation than the reciprocal plots and showed definite intercepts.

Effect of varying [HClO₄] : At constant [SNCB]₀ and [TSC]₀, the rates decreased with increase in [HClO₄] (Table 1) with inverse first order kinetics in [HClO₄]. The plots of k_{obs} versus 1/[HClO₄] also gave straight lines passing through the origin.

Effect of varying other parameters of the medium : The rates slightly decreased with increase in ionic strength of the medium (0.05–0.50 mol dm⁻³), but increased with decrease in dielectric constant of the medium, effected by increasing the methanol composition of solvent. Addition of the reduced product of the oxidant, benzamide had no significant effect on the rate.

The rates were measured at different temperatures

(288–308 K) for all the oxidations and the activation parameters computed from the Arrhenius and Eyring plots as described under discussion.

The probable reactive species in partial aqueous acid solutions of *N*-chlorobenzamide are ArCONHCl, (ArCONH₂Cl)⁺ and possibly HOCl or H₂O⁺Cl³.

Oxidation of [TSC] by all the oxidants followed first order kinetics in [SNCB], fractional order in [TSC] and inverse first order in [H⁺]. Further, the direct plots of k_{obs} versus [TSC] gave better correlation than the reciprocal plots, while k_{obs} versus 1/[H⁺] plot was linear. These results have been explained by a two-pathway mechanism (Scheme 1).

Path 1 :

Path 2 :

followed by other fast steps.

Scheme 1

The related rate laws are

$$-\frac{d[\text{SNCB}]}{dt} = \frac{K_1 k_2 [\text{SNCB}] [\text{H}_2\text{O}]}{[\text{H}^+]} + \frac{K_3 k_4 [\text{SNCB}] [\text{SH}^+]}{[\text{H}^+]} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{or } k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{K_1 k_2 [\text{H}_2\text{O}]}{[\text{H}^+]} + \frac{K_3 k_4 [\text{SH}^+]}{[\text{H}^+]} = \frac{k}{[\text{H}^+]} + \frac{k' [\text{SH}^+]}{[\text{H}^+]} \quad (2)$$

where, $k = K_1 k_2 [\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ and $k' = K_3 k_4$

$$\text{or } k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{1\{k + k' [\text{SH}^+]\}}{[\text{H}^+]} \quad (3)$$

The observed linearity of the plots of k_{obs} versus [substrate] and k_{obs} versus 1/[H⁺] are in accordance with the rate law (3). Further, the constants k and k' were computed from the intercepts and slopes of the plots of k_{obs} versus [substrate]. The computed constants were used to recalculate the rate constants from the rate law (2) as the [H⁺] was varied (Table 3). As can be seen, there is a good agreement between the recalculated values and the experimental con-

Table 3. Comparison of recalculated constants and experimental values for the oxidation of TSC by substituted *N*-chlorobenzamides (SNCB) in aqueous methanol (1 : 1, v/v) in the presence of perchloric acid

10^3 [SNCB] = 10^2 [TSC] = 3.33, $I = 1.0$ mol dm⁻³, Temp. = 303 K

$10^5 k_{\text{obs}}$ (s⁻¹) at different T (K) for p -X-C₆H₄CONHCl, where X =

10^2 [HClO ₄] mol dm ⁻³	H		<i>p</i> -CH ₃		<i>p</i> -Cl		<i>p</i> -NO ₂	
	Recalc.	Expt.	Recalc.	Expt.	Recalc.	Expt.	Recalc.	Expt.
1.0	46.6	44.0	41.6	38.4	54.7	57.2	51.5	54.6
2.0	23.3	23.0	20.8	19.5	27.3	24.8	25.7	24.8
3.0	15.5	12.5	13.8	11.1	18.2	14.4	17.1	16.6
5.0	9.3	7.8	8.3	7.5	10.9	9.2	10.3	10.0
10.0	4.6	4.5	4.1	4.0	5.4	5.3	5.2	5.2
20.0	2.3	2.1	2.1	2.0	2.7	2.6	2.6	2.9

Table 4. Activation parameters for the kinetics of oxidation of TSC by substituted *N*-chlorobenzamides (SNCB) in aqueous methanol (1 : 1, v/v) in presence of perchloric acid at 303 K

Parameter	<i>p</i> -X-C ₆ H ₄ CONHCl, where X =							
	H		<i>p</i> -CH ₃		<i>p</i> -Cl		<i>p</i> -NO ₂	
	Path 1	Path 2	Path 1	Path 2	Path 1	Path 2	Path 1	Path 2
E_a (kJ mol ⁻¹)	91.9	91.9	90.4	84.0	84.9	115.0	107.2	58.4
log A	11.4	13.0	11.1	12.8	10.3	16.9	14.1	7.0
ΔH^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	89.35	76.0	88.2	76.6	81.7	113.6	102.8	56.1
ΔS^\ddagger (J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	-36.28	-48.5	-39.9	-49.3	-58.9	72.97	10.2	-118.2
ΔG^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	100.3	90.7	100.2	91.5	99.5	91.5	99.7	91.9
Optimised values corresponding to log A value of NCB ^a								
E_a (kJ mol ⁻¹)	92.2	91.8	92.2	92.6	91.4	92.6	91.4	93.1
ΔH^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	89.7	89.3	89.7	90.1	88.9	90.1	88.9	90.5
ΔG^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	100.3	90.7	100.3	91.5	99.5	91.5	99.7	91.9
Optimised values corresponding to E_a value of NCB ^b								
log A	11.3	13.0	11.3	12.9	11.5	12.9	11.5	12.8
ΔS^\ddagger (J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	-36.1	-4.3	-4.3	-6.9	-33.4	-6.9	-33.6	-8.3
ΔG^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	100.3	90.7	90.7	91.5	99.5	91.5	99.6	91.9

^aThe energies of activations of all the substituted *N*-chlorobenzamides were optimised corresponding to the log A value of NCB using the equation, $E_a = 2.303 RT (\log A - \log k_{\text{obs}})$.

^blog A values of all the substituted *N*-chlorobenzamides were optimised corresponding to the E_a value of NCB through the equation, $\log A = \log k_{\text{obs}} + E_a/2.303 RT$.

stants testing the validity of the rate law (2). Further, the constants k and k' were calculated from the plots of k_{obs} versus [TSC] at different temperatures by varying [TSC] at each temperature for all the oxidations. These calculated constants were used to compute activation parameters for paths 1 and 2 from the plots of log k_i versus $1/T$ and log (k_i/T) versus $1/T$ (where k_i is either k or k') (Table 4).

Effective oxidising species of the oxidants employed in the present oxidations is Cl⁺ in different forms. Thus the oxidising strength of the oxidant depends on the ease with which it is released in the reaction system from the respective oxidants, which in turn depends on the electron environment around the N-Cl bond or in other words on the polarisation of the chlorine atom in the bond N-Cl. Hence, the introduction of different substituent groups in the benzene ring of the oxidant affects the ability of the reagent to oxidise a substrate. Therefore, it is expected that the electron-releasing groups such as CH₃, inhibit the ease with which Cl⁺ is released from an oxidant, while electron-withdrawing groups such as Cl, NO₂ etc., enhance this ability. The present observations are in conformity with these trends. Decrease in rate of oxidation in going from

NCCB to NCNB may be due to the steric hindrance. Nevertheless the rate with both NCCB and NCNB are greater than that with NCB.

The applicability of Hammett equation⁴ has also been tested. The plot of log k_{obs} versus σ_p are reasonably linear and the following relation was found to be valid,

$$\log k_{\text{obs}} = -3.45 + 0.36 \sigma_p \quad (4)$$

Further, the energies of activations of all the substituted *N*-chlorobenzamides were optimised corresponding to the log A value of NCB using the equation, $E_a = 2.303 RT (\log A - \log k_{\text{obs}})$. Similarly, log A values of all the substituted *N*-chlorobenzamides were optimised corresponding to the E_a value of NCB through the equation, $\log A = \log k_{\text{obs}} + E_a/2.303 RT$. The free energies of activation remain almost the same in both the optimisations. This may signal the operation of similar mechanisms in all the cases. The formation of more ordered activated complexes is evident from the negative values of ΔS^\ddagger . Further, the relatively high positive free energies of activation and negative entropy of activation may indicate the role of bond-breaking in attaining the activated state. The plots of ΔH^\ddagger versus

ΔS^\ddagger for both the sets of values were linear with isokinetic temperatures of 297 and 307 K, respectively.

Several approaches have been put forward to explain, quantitatively, the effect of dielectric constant of the medium on the rates of ion-ion, ion-dipolar molecule and dipolar molecule-dipolar molecule reactions in the liquid phase⁵⁻⁷. For the limiting case of zero angle of approach between an ion and a dipole, Amis⁶ showed that a plot of $\log k_D$ versus $1/D$ gives a straight-line with a positive slope for the reaction between a positive ion and a dipolar molecule,

$$\log k_D = \log k_\infty + \frac{Z_e \mu}{2.303 k_B T r^2 D} \quad (5)$$

where k_∞ is the rate constant in a medium of infinite dielectric constant, μ the dipole moment of the dipolar molecule, Z_e the charge on the ion, r the radius and T the absolute temperature. The present experimental observations, i.e. increase of rate with decrease in dielectric constant of the medium (by increasing the methanol composition of the medium) is in agreement with ion-dipolar molecule interactions and the reaction pathways suggested to explain the kinetic results. The observed effect may also be explained by the Laidler-Eyring equation⁷,

$$\log k_D = \log k_\infty + \frac{Z^2 e^2}{2Dk_B T} \left[\frac{1}{r} - \frac{1}{r_\ddagger} \right] \quad (6)$$

where r and r_\ddagger refer to the radii of the reactant species and activated complex, respectively. It is seen that the rate should be greater in a medium of lower dielectric constant when $r_\ddagger > r$. It is likely that the radii of the activated complexes in the present cases are greater than the reactant molecules as the reaction involves the interaction between positive ions and dipolar molecules.

Experimental

N-Chlorobenzamide (NCB) was prepared by passing a continuous stream of dry chlorine gas into a hot saturated solution of benzamide in hydrochloric acid⁸. The crystals separated were washed with cold water and crystallised from alcohol (m.p. 116°).

N-Chloro-*p*-methylbenzamide, *N*-chloro-*p*-chlorobenzamide and *N*-chloro-*p*-nitrobenzamide were prepared as follows. The respective substituted benzoic acids were added to thionyl chloride and thoroughly mixed. The residual benzoyl chloride was mixed with liquor ammonia and the reaction mixtures were cooled in ice-water. The precipitated substituted benzamides were filtered, washed and crystallised from hot water. They were characterised by recording their melting points: *p*-chlorobenzamide, m.p. 172–176°, *p*-methylbenzamide, 161–163° and *p*-nitrobenzamide, 199–201°, and further characterised by their IR spectra (Jasco 430 FTIR spectrometer). These substituted benzamides were then *N*-chlorinated by a similar procedure. The purity of all the *N*-chloro compounds was checked by the

iodometric estimation of the amount of active chlorine present. They were further characterised by recording their melting points (NCMB, 153.5–154.5°; NCCB, 196–198°; NCNB, 232–233°) and IR spectra. The stock solution (0.10 mol dm⁻³) of *N*-chlorobenzamide and substituted-*N*-chlorobenzamides were prepared in methanol, standardised by the iodometric method and stored in dark brown bottles.

Thiosemicarbazide (E. Merck) was purified by recrystallisation from hot water, and its aqueous stock solution (0.20 mol dm⁻³) was prepared in double-distilled water. Other reagents employed were of A.R. grade. Ionic strength of the medium was maintained at 0.30 mol dm⁻³ using concentrated aqueous solution of sodium nitrate.

Kinetic measurements : The reactions were carried out in glass stoppered pyrex boiling tubes under pseudo-first order conditions with [substrate] \gg [oxidant] (5 to 50 times). The reactions were initiated by the rapid addition of requisite amounts of oxidant solution (0.0002–0.002 mol dm⁻³), thermally pre-equilibrated at a desired temperature, to solution mixtures containing known amounts of the substrate (0.005–0.05 mol dm⁻³), perchloric acid (0.01–0.2 mol dm⁻³), sodium nitrate, water and methanol (to maintain 1 : 1, v/v solvent composition), thermostated at the same temperature. The progress of the reactions was monitored for two half-lives by the iodometric estimation of unreacted oxidant at regular time intervals. The pseudo-first order rate constants (k_{obs}) computed by the graphical methods were reproducible within $\pm 4\%$ error.

Stoichiometry and product analysis : The stoichiometries of the reactions of TSC with NCB, NCMB, NCCB and NCNB were determined by allowing the reactions to go to completion at room temperature and at different [HClO₄] (0.02 to 0.20 mol dm⁻³) and [oxidant]/[substrate] ratios. The products of oxidations were identified by the standard tests⁹. Sulfate in the reaction products was estimated gravimetrically by precipitating it as barium sulfate¹⁰. The yields were $95 \pm 4\%$. Further, chloride and cyanide were also estimated by precipitating them as AgCl and AgCN, respectively. Nitrogen liberated was determined quantitatively by making use of Schiff's nitrometer. A slow and steady current of pure and dry CO₂ was passed through the reaction vessel to sweep off N₂ to the nitrometer filled with 50% KOH, where CO₂ was completely absorbed. The volume of N₂ was noted and compared with the theoretical value. Benzamide was almost quantitatively precipitated when the solution containing the reaction products was concentrated to remove the methanol content of the solvent and cooled. The observed stoichiometry per mole of TSC may be represented as

where, Ar = X-C₆H₄; X = H, CH₃, Cl, NO₂.

Note

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